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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**3-Multipolarity of the Global Space: Strategic
Understanding of Geopolitical Trends. By
Viacheslav Kolotov and others. p. 55**

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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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**MULTIPOLARITY OF THE GLOBAL
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ABSTRACT

This article explores polycentrism as a defining feature of the emerging world order. It examines how the shift from a unipolar to a polycentric international system transforms global power dynamics, fosters regionalization, and reshapes international relations. The study focuses on the growing influence of regional centers formed around economically and politically strong states and associations. It highlights the increasing autonomy of semi-peripheral countries that create independent axes of influence, weakening traditional global dominants. As polycentrism advances, foreign policy strategies shift from hierarchical dominance to more flexible, multilateral approaches, enabling middle-ranked states to pursue cooperation, neutrality, or strategic confrontation. Regionalization emerges as a key driver in forming a mosaic-like global structure, where macro-regions act as autonomous power centers. Strengthened regional integration and leadership allow these regions to project influence globally, contributing to a decentralized but interconnected polycentric order supported by economic specialization and dynamic coalitions.

Keywords: polycentrism, global governance, regionalization, geopolitics, multipolarity.

1- INTRODUCTION

The current phase of the world order is becoming an arena of revolutionary transformations taking place against the backdrop of growing systemic instability, increasingly frequent manifestations of conflict and rethinking of traditional approaches to the organization of international life. The scientific and expert discourse is increasingly dominated by alarming assessments: the international system is entering a phase of deep turmoil, the main signs of which are the growth of offensive nationalism, a departure from established norms and imperatives of international behavior, the erosion of deterrence and balancing mechanisms, an increase in geopolitical turbulence and unpredictability of key actors' actions.¹

The world political system is increasingly showing signs of dispersion of centers of influence, when the dominance of one superpower or a coordinated group of countries gives way to multilevel and multi-vector interaction between independent poles of power. The new polycentricity itself is accompanied by competition of norms, institutions, and strategic visions of the future, which complicates the formation of a unified and stable architecture of international security and cooperation. At the same time, these transformations should not be viewed as inherently fatal or destructive. Rather, it is a change in the parameters of the international order, which requires an

¹ Lama, F. (2023). *Why the West can't win: From Bretton Woods to a multipolar world*. Clarity Press. <https://www.amazon.com/Why-West-Cant-Win-Multipolar/dp/1949762742>

analytical understanding of their content, practical implications for global governance, and new models of behavior of key international players.² Thus, the relevance of studying the polycentrism of the modern world order is due not only to the need to rethink the fundamental principles of the last decades of the world order, but also to practical demands for new approaches to ensuring stability, security and effective polycentric governance in the context of profound civilizational changes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Studies of the polycentricity of the modern world order point to profound political transformations accompanying the transition to a multipolar structure of international relations. Cheong³ and Kholod et al.⁴ emphasize that polycentrism is not only a geopolitical or economic category, but also a political dynamic that requires new institutional thinking to adapt to changes in global governance. At the same time, these scholars do not sufficiently reveal the processes of updating the structure of international relations and adapting to new forms of interstate rivalry and coexistence. Researchers Ashford and Cooper,⁵ Perskaya⁶ and Thapa⁷ emphasize the multidimensional structure of international interaction, where geostrategic spaces are formed on the basis of economic interdependence, political compatibility and ideological narratives. However, it should be noted that they do not fully describe the essence of polycentrism as a network of blocs with varying degrees of autonomy and influence, where each center of power forms its own rules of the game, creating precedents for alternative global governance.

² Wardhani, N. F. (2021). The concept of polarity and centres of power in international relations. *Jurnal Politik Indonesia*, 7(2), 106–111. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jpi.v7i2.31126>

³ Cheong, J. (2018). Polycentrism in Majority World theologizing: An engagement with power and essentialism. In A. Yeh & T. Tiénou (Eds.), *Majority world theologies: Theologizing from Africa, Asia, Latin America, and the ends of the earth* (Vol. 26, pp. 24–40). William Carey Library. https://www.academia.edu/74278511/Polycentrism_in_Majority_World_theologizing

⁴ Kholod, B., Zadoia, O. A., & Zadoia, A. A. (2020). Polycentrism of the modern world: A methodology for discovering world leaders. *Naukovyi Visnyk Natsionalnoho Hirnychoho Universytetu*, 3, 171–176. <https://doi.org/10.33271/nvngu/2020-3/171>

⁵ Ashford, E., & Cooper, E. (2023). *Assumption testing: Multipolarity is more dangerous than bipolarity for the United States*. Stimson Center. <https://www.stimson.org/2023/assumption-testing-multipolarity-is-more-dangerous-than-bipolarity-for-the-united-states/>

⁶ Perskaya, V. V. (2023). Polycentrism in international relations and globalization processes. In *Capitalism – Theories and empirics in a new dawn*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.105580>

⁷ Thapa, R. (2025). Uncommon reality: Finding the unipolar world in bipolar and multipolar discourses. *Unity Journal*, 6(1), 184–201. <https://doi.org/10.3126/unityj.v6i1.75592>

Within the framework of radical geography, Ablazov et al.⁸ and Çeviköz⁹ criticize classical geopolitical paradigms that simplified world politics into a binary division into dependent and independent countries. Instead, they argue that a polycentric structure involves the interaction of numerous political actors with their own legitimacy, political traditions, and conflicting visions of the global future. The criticism of classical geopolitical paradigms proposed by these researchers is not accompanied by a clear definition of how the multiplicity of political actors generates new challenges, including competition for political leadership in the absence of a single normative system.

Post-neoclassical theorists, such as Laffaye et al.¹⁰ and Tizzard,¹¹ note that it is impossible to create a single model of world order, as states and regional blocs act on the basis of their own ideas of order, which leads to a gap between political practice and global normativity. Gürcan¹² and Morin and Couette¹³ add that the formation of a polycentric world is complicated by differences in power potential, perceptions of legitimacy, justice, and the functioning of international law. However, it is worth pointing out that the positions of Rapanyane¹⁴ and Schreiber et al.,¹⁵ who study regulatory mechanisms in the political model of interstate interaction and highlight the role of international organizations, are also noteworthy. They do not show the institutional inertia of international organizations such as the United Nations (further –

⁸ Ablazov, I., Abramov, V., Vereshchak, V., Mishkov, O., & Khamula, S. (2021). Polycentrism of the modern world as a geopolitical reality. *AD ALTA: Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 11(2), 224–228. https://www.magnanimitas.cz/ADALTA/110224/papers/A_39.pdf

⁹ Çeviköz, Ü. (2025). Polycentrism or multipolarity: Understanding the contemporary international system. *Global Panorama*. <https://www.globalpanorama.org/en/2025/01/polycentrism-or-multipolarity-understanding-the-contemporary-international-system-unal-cevikoz/>

¹⁰ Laffaye, S., Lavopa, F., & Pérez Llana, C. (2013). Changes in the global economic power structure: Towards a multipolar world? *CEI Argentine Journal of International Economics*, 1, 1–21. https://cancilleria.gob.ar/userfiles/ut/changes_in_the_global_economic_power_structure_towards_a_multipolar_world.pdf

¹¹ Tizzard, D. A. (2017). American unipolarity: The uneven distribution of power. *Global Politics Review*, 3(2), 10–25. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1238465>

¹² Gürcan, E. C. (2020). The construction of “posthegemonic multipolarity” in Eurasia: A comparative perspective. *The Japanese Political Economy*, 46(2–3), 127–151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2329194X.2020.1839911>

¹³ Morin, J.-F., & Couette, C. (2025). The missing ingredients for a polycentric governance system of orbital debris. *Global Environmental Politics*, 25(2), 1–25. https://doi.org/10.1162/glep_a_00775

¹⁴ Rapanyane, B. M. (2020). The new world [dis]order in the complexity of multipolarity: United States of America’s hegemonic decline and the configuration of new power patterns. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 21(5), Article e2114. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pa.2114>

¹⁵ Schreiber, D., Hassnaoui, S., Weyembergh, A., Brosig, M., Kanifa, K., & Tibaingana, A. (2025). From polycrisis to polysolutions: An interdisciplinary approach to complex global challenges. *PolyCIVIS*, 1. <https://civis.eu/storage/files/1foundational-brief-polycrisis-and-policy-series-formatted-version2-schreiber-et-al-mar-2025.pdf>

UN) in response to the crisis of global governance, nor do they offer specific tools for synchronizing interests between the main players in the context of multipolarity.

The studies by Peters,¹⁶ Yeros,¹⁷ and Zvezdanović Lobanova and Nikolić,¹⁸ which use quantitative analysis methods, confirm the redistribution of political and geographical forces between China and the United States. At the same time, traditional centers of power retain leadership in the military, technological, and institutional spheres.¹⁹ Lofthouse and Kral²⁰ note that the COVID-19 pandemic has become a catalyst for the establishment of a multipolar order, exposing the vulnerability of centralized governance models and promoting regional autonomy. Already Attinà,²¹ Burton,²² Makedon et al.²³ propose to interpret polycentrism as a mosaic structure that manifests itself in different ways in different areas of international relations. However, the works of these authors emphasize economic potential as a key factor in determining the role of the state in the global order. There is also a lack of a comprehensive analysis of the mechanisms of coordination and synchronization of interests in a polycentric world, which leaves open the question of effective global governance in the context of multiple centers of power.

Thus, authors can identify a scientific gap in the issue of polycentric adaptation to modern forms of interstate rivalry and coexistence, which remains insufficiently studied. The modern version of polycentrism is not considered as a network of autonomous centers of power that create alternative models of global governance, and there is a lack of analysis of their interaction and mutual influence.

¹⁶ Peters, M. A. (2023). The emerging multipolar world order: A preliminary analysis. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 55(14), 1653–1663. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2022.2151896>

¹⁷ Yeros, P. (2024). A polycentric world will only be possible by the intervention of the “Sixth Great Power.” *Agrarian South: Journal of Political Economy*, 13(1), 14–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/22779760241230679>

¹⁸ Zvezdanović Lobanova, J., & Nikolić, G. (2024). Does the concept of multipolarity accurately reflect the current geopolitical reality? *The Review of International Affairs*, 75(1191), 261–277. https://doi.org/10.18485/iipe_ria.2024.75.1191.4

¹⁹ Wyne, A. (2023). The dangers of detachment: Why economic independence could make the world more dangerous. *Foreign Affairs*. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/china/dangers-detachment-economic-independence-dangerous>

²⁰ Lofthouse, J. K., & Kral, L. (2025). A polycentric approach for addressing wicked social problems. *Administrative Sciences*, 15(1), Article 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci15010022>

²¹ Attinà, F. (2025). Europe and IndoPacific in the world order transition. *Romanian Journal of European Affairs*, 25(1), 26–42. https://rjea.ier.gov.ro/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/RJEA_vol.25_no.1_2025_final.pdf

²² Burton, G. (2021). Middle power behavior under multipolarity: Indonesia and Malaysia in the Middle East since the Arab uprisings. *Asian Politics & Policy*, 13(2), 228–247. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aspp.12577>

²³ Makedon, V. V., Valikov, V. P., & Koshlyak, E. E. (2020). The global labor market in the coordinates of the digital economy. *Academic Review*, 52(1), 91–107. <https://doi.org/10.32342/2074-5354-2020-1-52-9>

The purpose of the article is to study the phenomenon of polycentrism as a fundamental characteristic of the modern world order, which is being formed in the context of the transformation of the global balance of power, the growth of regional centers of influence and the erosion of traditional mechanisms of hegemonic domination.

3. METHOD

The study used three interrelated methods of research: The method of geopolitical analysis with a focus on the spatial model, modeling of global political processes, and systematic study of civilizational and geographical structures to trace structural shifts in the geography of global forces and highlight the dynamics of the formation of a new world political core. The method of modeling geopolitical processes is used to build a structural model of the modern polycentric system, taking into account the interaction between key actors: The United States of America (further – USA), China, India, European Union (further – EU) and regional blocs. The method of systematic study of geocivilizations created the basis for the study to go beyond material factors and determine the deep foundations of modern polycentrism. In this context, states and regions were not considered in isolation, but as parts of broader civilizational communities with their own cultural codes, values, historical and political memory, and strategic claims.

4. RESULTS

4.1. CHANGES AND TRANSFORMATIONS IN THE GLOBAL ORDER MODEL

In the context of the growing instability of the international system and the transformation of the global balance of power, the concept of polycentrism is gaining increasing theoretical and practical significance as a key characteristic of the latest stage of global development. Modern analysts are increasingly pointing out that the global architecture of security and economic cooperation is gradually moving away from the unipolarity that has long been dominant, and instead is establishing a multi-level model with numerous regional and global centers of power. Thus, Røren²⁴ argues that authors are witnessing a return to a multipolar state of international relations, which is manifested in the growing influence of countries such as China, India, Brazil, Russia, as well as a number of leading European states: Great Britain, Germany. France, whose economic growth, if there is political will, can be transformed into strategic autonomy on the global stage by 2050. The world space, according to modern theoretical approaches, is divided into three main categories that reflect the unevenness of economic development and the degree of influence on the global system:

²⁴ Røren, P. (2024). Unipolarity is not over yet. *Global Studies Quarterly*, 4(2), Article ksae018. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isagsq/ksae018>

- global core (centers). The core, or global centers, represented mainly by the G7 countries, such as the United States, Japan, Germany, the United Kingdom, France, Italy, and Canada, are characterized by a high level of economic development, technological superiority, and significant influence on the formation of global economic and political rules, which allows them to maintain a leading role in the world economy and determine the direction of globalization.²⁵

- the semi-periphery includes countries that are at an intermediate stage of development, such as China, India, Brazil, Russia, or South Africa, which, although demonstrating significant economic growth and regional influence, have not yet reached the level of global centers, but are actively seeking greater autonomy and weight in a polycentric world by forming their own regional economic axes and integration platforms.

- the periphery, which includes the least developed countries, in particular sub-Saharan Africa and some Latin American countries, is characterized by limited access to global markets, low levels of industrialization, and dependence on economic support from centers and semi-peripheries, which makes them less influential in the global system, but at the same time important for the resource supply of the world economy.²⁶

In our opinion, the new format of interstate cooperation is becoming polycentric in nature, while the security architecture retains signs of unipolarity, and inter-polarity dominates in the field of environmental governance. The cultural and political sphere, on the contrary, is characterized by non-polarity, or dispersion of influence without clear dominants (Table 1).

Table 1. Polycentrism in the transformation of the global order: key dimensions and aspects

Aspect of polycentrism	Economic dimension	Security dimension	Political dimension	Cultural and political dimension
Transition from unipolarity	Growth of economic potential of countries (China, India, Brazil) contributes to the formation	Preservation of unipolarity in the security architecture due to the dominance of the United States	Emergence of regional centers of influence (e.g., the UK, Germany, France)	Dispersion of influence leading to non-polarity

²⁵ Thunder, D. (2025). *The polycentric republic: A theory of civil order for free and diverse societies*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003540182>

²⁶ Morin, J.-F., & Couette, C. (2025). *Id.*

	of new centers of power			
Regional autonomy	Economic interaction becomes polycentric due to the growth of regional economies	Regional autonomy policies backed by security instruments	Sovereign foreign policy of countries (e.g., Australia takes into account the influence of China)	Formation of regional cultural identities
Global shock (COVID-19)	Exposing the vulnerability of centralized economic models	Strengthening regional security strategies after the pandemic	Growing desire for independent foreign policy	Emphasis on local values in a global context
Weakening of US hegemony	Competition with China and other economic centers	Loss of the US role as the sole guarantor of security	Rise of alternative regional institutions	Adaptation of American leadership to new conditions
Bipolarity of the USA-China	Economic rivalry between the United States and China as the core of the new order	Potential confrontation over the "Thucydides' trap"	Polarization of global politics around two centers	Clash of values and narratives of the two superpowers
Mosaic structure	Polycentricity in economic interaction	Interpolarity in environmental governance	Polyphony in political relations	Non-polarity due to dispersion of cultural influence

Source: author's own elaboration

One of the central elements of academic discussions on the evolution of the modern international order is the question of the diminishing role of the United States as a traditional hegemon and the impact of this process on the formation of a polycentric configuration of the world order. In the context of the growing power of new centers of power, such as China, India, Brazil, and a number of regional alliances, more and more researchers point to the change in the established structures of dominance and the transition to a more fragmented and multidimensional international system.

The process of weakening US hegemony is clearly evident with several parallel processes: the growth of China's economic potential, the creation of alternative regional institutions that expand the autonomy of individual countries' foreign policies, and Washington's loss of the ability to be the sole guarantor of security for less powerful states. In this sense, multipolarity is interpreted not only as a geopolitical polyphony, but as a structure that allows more states to pursue their own interests without regard to the position of one dominant center.²⁷ Authors can say that in the foreseeable future, in a polycentric world, the United States will retain the status of one of the key powers, but will lose its exclusivity as the sole arbiter of international affairs. This approach significantly changes the paradigm of leadership: the role of the United States is increasingly assessed not as absolute, but as functionally adaptive, requiring constant rethinking in the face of growing competition from other players. At the same time, not all researchers tend to agree with the thesis of the decline of American influence. It is safe to say that the true polarity is determined not so much by regional power relations as by global imbalances, where the United States is still far ahead of other countries in terms of defense spending and power projection. In this sense, the attempts of individual countries to demonstrate geopolitical subjectivity do not always have the systemic ability to change the structure of the international hierarchy.²⁸

In parallel with the discussions about multipolarity, part of the academic community hypothesizes the formation of a new bipolar order, in which the main line of confrontation is between the United States and China. The well-known analyst Bomassi,²⁹ in particular, considers this through the prism of the concept of the Thucydides' trap, predicting a high probability of a conflict confrontation between the two superpowers in the near future. It is the Sino-American rivalry that is becoming the new core of a new geopolitical structure that will eclipse all other forms of political multipolarity in the next 25-30 years.

²⁷ Aligică, D. P., & Murtazashvili, J. (2025). Introduction: Modus vivendi and polycentric governance systems. In *Governing differences* (pp. 1–21). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781035348589.00006>

²⁸ Ganchev, I. (2025). Trump's new foreign policy: Strategic repositioning in a multipolar world. *Regional Project Initiative*, 7. <https://regionalintegration.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/RPI-2025-7-Ganchev-I.pdf>

²⁹ Bomassi, L. (2025). The geopolitics of multipolarity: Europe's role in the IndoPacific. *European Union Institute for Security Studies*, 2025(03). https://www.iss.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2025-02/Brief_2025-03_Indo-Pacific.pdf

Based on these approaches, several key points should be specifically identified for understanding polycentrism within the current international reality:

- first, the growing political, economic, and military potential of new actors (both individual states and regional alliances) creates preconditions for the formation of a more complex multi-vector system of global governance;
- secondly, the loss of the US monopoly role is not final, but requires a flexible restructuring of its international leadership strategy;
- thirdly, despite the growing political autonomy of individual states, polarization around the two main centers of power, the United States and China, is still a likely trajectory for the development of the world order.

4.2. POLYCENTRISM THROUGH THE LENS OF NEOREALISM: INTERSYSTEMIC INFLUENCES AND TRANSFORMATION OF STATE BEHAVIOR

Within the neorealist approach to the analysis of international relations, the key methodological principle is to define the level of the international system as an object that shapes the nature and direction of the actions of actor states. It is in this context that more and more researchers interpret polycentrism as an inherent feature of the modern global order, which directly affects both the structure of interstate interaction and the specifics of the implementation of foreign policy strategies. Polycentrism is interpreted not only as a geopolitical reality that reflects the presence of several centers of power, but also as a factor that changes the logic of decision-making in the field of peace and security. In the context of growing multipolarity, the key is not hierarchical dominance, but the structure of bilateral or regional relations between the great powers – primarily the United States, China, and the EU.

In this context, the words of the authoritative American diplomat H. Kissinger, who emphasized that none of the leading countries called upon to create a new international system has the relevant historical experience of existing in a multistate, deeply fragmented global environment, resonate extremely well.³⁰ According to his vision, the new world order is being formed in conditions of unprecedented conceptual diversity and ideological polarization, on a scale previously unimaginable in human history. In addition, Buxton insists that building a stable global system cannot be achieved by the efforts of even the most powerful state, as an effective world order requires collective responsibility and a common vision that must be in tune with many national identities and civilizational traditions.³¹ This thesis was confirmed against the

³⁰ Martill, B., & ten Brinke, L. (2020). *Europe in a multipolar world (Strategic update)*. LSE IDEAS, London School of Economics and Political Science. <https://eprints.lse.ac.uk/107579/>

³¹ Buxton, N., Tooze, A., Bello, W., Alami, I., DiCarlo, J., Rolf, S., Schindler, S., Font, T., Ziadah, R., Garcia, A., Starrs, S. K., Wray, B., Mahjoub, H., Lovera, J., Anugrah, I., Hung, K. H., & Malik, S. (2025). *Geopolitics of capitalism: State of Power 2025*. Transnational Institute. https://www.tni.org/files/2025-02/State-of-Power-2025-web_3.pdf

backdrop of Russia's military aggression against Ukraine, when an international coalition of both military and macro-financial assistance to Ukraine was formed. This understanding of polycentrism as a factor of stabilization of the international system was formed after the events of September 11, when the international system entered an era of multipolar antagonism, in which direct military confrontations between key actors are becoming less likely, while indirect conflicts are more frequent, realized through third parties or within local arenas of confrontation.

In the same vein, it is worth emphasizing the analytical approach of Schreiber et al.,³² who introduce the concept of peacetime warfare as a new norm for the era of polycentrism. According to their definition, the absence of large-scale hostilities between the world's major powers is not evidence of peace, as the conflict continues in the form of cyber confrontation, information wars, and hybrid attacks on energy and infrastructure security. This indicates the evolution of forms of influence characteristic of a multipolar system, where classical forms of confrontation are transformed into more sophisticated, indirect strategies of domination.

One of the consequences of the multipolar environment is the increased freedom of maneuver for the middle group countries. The foreign policies of Malaysia and Indonesia demonstrate that in a blurred global hierarchy, these states are able to simultaneously pursue strategies of cooperation, confrontation, and neutrality in their relations with regional leaders, which was impossible under conditions of rigid bipolarity or unipolar hegemony. The analysis of the situation in the MENA region (Middle East and North Africa), which is gradually moving to a state of competitive multipolarity, deepens the understanding of this dynamic.³³ There is a growing rejection of stable geopolitical alliances in favor of situational coalitions based on functional rather than ideological or value-based principles. Active polycentric processes also have direct implications for regional alliances in the event of a potential conflict between superpowers. There is a clear pattern that the US allies in the Indo-Pacific region may be inclined to use the tactic of “buck-passing”, i.e. avoiding direct involvement in conflicts by shifting the initiative to other players.³⁴ In general, polycentrism within the neorealist paradigm can be interpreted as a systemic property of the international order that determines the nature of state behavior, creates a new configuration of influence, and opens up space for diversified strategies and alliances in foreign policy.

³² Schreiber et al. (2025). *Id.*

³³ Chan, B. (2025, January 30). Era of multipolar world marks a historic shift in global dynamics. *China Daily*. <https://www.chinadailyasia.com/article/607668>

³⁴ Richey, M. (2020). Buck-passing, chain-ganging and alliances in the multipolar IndoAsiaPacific. *The International Spectator*, 55(2), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03932729.2019.1706390>

4.3. REGIONALIZATION AS A BASIS FOR POLYCENTRISM OF THE CURRENT AND FUTURE POLITICAL SYSTEM

Current significant regional processes are increasingly influencing the global configuration of political power and the architecture of international interaction, and the concept of polycentrism is enriched with new semantic dimensions precisely by integrating the provisions of the regional approach to the analysis of the world order. The growing role of macro-regional entities, regional powers and integration associations significantly modifies the idea of which actors form the newest multipolar model of the world system.

Unlike the classical realism paradigm, which focuses mainly on the nation-state as the main actor in international politics, the modern model of polycentrism emphasizes macro-regional complexes, which are the prototypes of the newest centers of power in the emerging world system. The emergence of global regions as qualitatively new geopolitical phenomena, which are at the same time functional blocks of the polycentric world and points of condensation of political, economic and civilizational power, is becoming a fact. The existing multipolarity in the twenty-first century is not limited to the list of leading powers, but is manifested in the interaction of integral regional systems that function as autonomous centers of influence. The thesis about the relationship between the growing regionalization and the emergence of a polycentric world is supported by a number of contemporary researchers who point out that the loss of the dominant role of the United States opens the way to the formation of regional orders within which the leading states of certain parts of the world can fill the resulting vacuum of influence.³⁵

Current political scenarios emphasize the growing role of Eurasian regionalism, which is gaining particular importance as the basis for an alternative model of geopolitical multipolarity. In this sense, the creation of structures such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization or the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank is interpreted as a manifestation of regional self-assertion that can change the balance of power on the world stage. At the same time, a model of "regional polarity" is being formed, according to which none of the new powerful states is able to completely replace the United States at the global level, but each of them dominates within a particular region. This model is becoming a kind of mosaic structure of the world order, in which the world is divided into influential regions, and global multipolarity is formed from below, through the growth of regional autonomies and ties.³⁶ Authors note the rapid spread of decentralized polycentrism, in which regional leaders can not only dominate their macro-areas, but also actively project their influence beyond the regions by establishing flexible and

³⁵Plotnikov, O. (2025). Formation of world multipolarity and its impact on the development of Ukraine. *Economy of Ukraine*, 68(3), 50–62. <https://doi.org/10.15407/economyukr.2025.03.050>

³⁶ Cooley, A., & Nexon, D. (2020). *Exit from hegemony: The unraveling of the American global order*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/48655669>

unstable interregional coalitions. The construct is already in line with the idea of “new regionalism”, which provides for greater foreign policy freedom for member states of regional associations, including through the establishment of unpredictable alliances outside their geographic space.

In the context of the new polycentric world order, special attention should be paid to countries such as China and India, which are demonstrating a dynamic change in their international status, which is leading to a transformation of regional and global balances of power. While China has already effectively consolidated its position as one of the key centers of power, India, given its economic growth and the intensification of its foreign policy, is approaching a similar level of influence.³⁷ The strengthening of their geopolitical weight is increasingly seen not as a situational phenomenon, but as a long-term trend that can change the entire structure of the international system. Authors should also include those states that, although they do not have the formal status of global leaders, are increasingly claiming to be part of the core of the world's political system. Such ambitions are often based not on legal or institutional criteria, but on real achievements in foreign policy, economics, or security. A new trend is the emergence in this circle of countries that until recently were on the periphery of international attention, but today are beginning to form their own identity as independent geopolitical players.³⁸

In the context of the emergence of a polycentric model of the world order, international trade continues to be one of the key markers of global interdependence, which is simultaneously influenced by new geopolitical realities. The analysis of the dynamics of global trade in 2016-2025 shows a steady increase in its volumes in nominal terms: during this time, global exports of goods and services grew from 20.8 trillion USD. The global exports of goods and services grew from 20.8 trillion US dollars to the projected 33.5 trillion US dollars. That is, more than 1.6 times (Table 2).³⁹

³⁷ Ashford, E., & Cooper, E. (2023). *Id.*

³⁸ Makedon, V., Trachova, D., Myronchuk, V., Opalchuk, R., & Davydenko, O. (2024). The development and characteristics of sustainable finance. In A. Hamdan (Ed.), *Achieving sustainable business through AI, technology education and computer science* (Vol. 163, pp. 373–382). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-73632-2_31

³⁹ World Trade Organization. (2024). *World trade report 2024: Trade and inclusiveness – How to make trade work for all.* https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/publications_e/wtr24_e.htm

Table 2. Dynamics of global economic growth and transformation of international trade in the context of the formation of a polycentric world order (trillion US dollars, %)

Indicator	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
GDP										
World, trillion dollars	76,6	81,5	86,5	87,8	85,5	97,4	101,4	105,7	110,0	115,4
World, growth,	3,3	3,8	3,6	2,9	-2,7	6,6	3,6	3,3	3,2	3,3
Countries of the global core	1,8	2,6	2,3	1,9	-4,0	6,0	2,9	1,7	1,8	1,8
Peripheral and semi-peripheral countries	4,4	4,8	4,7	3,7	-1,8	7,0	4,0	4,4	4,2	4,2
International trade, exports										
Goods and services, trillion dollars	20,8	23,0	25,2	24,8	22,4	28,1	31,6	30,9	32,2	33,5

Indicator	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Growth, %	-1,8	10,4	9,5	-1,5	-9,7	25,5	12,2	-1,9	4,2	3,9
Countries of the global core										
Volume, trillion dollars	13,5	14,9	16,4	16,1	14,6	18,3	20,5	20,1	20,9	21,8
Growth, %	-2,5	8,5	8,0	-2,0	-10,5	23,0	10,5	-2,5	3,5	3,2
Countries of the periphery and semi-periphery										
Volume, trillion dollars	7,2	8,1	8,8	8,7	7,8	9,8	11,0	10,8	11,3	11,7
Growth, %	-0,5	13,0	11,5	-0,5	-8,5	29,0	14,5	-0,8	5,5	5,0

Source: World Trade Organization⁴⁰

This increase is significant given the presence of a number of crisis factors that have complicated trade dynamics, including the trade confrontation between the US and China, escalation of regional conflicts, and disruption of global supply chains caused by the war in Ukraine.

Such dynamics of global economic processes is a direct reflection of the international community's adaptation to the new conditions of a multipolar world, in which the stabilization of strategic markets, including raw materials and energy, increasingly depends not only on economic factors but also on political interaction

⁴⁰ World Trade Organization. (2024). *Id.*

between new centers of power. The partial stabilization of prices for key resources observed in recent years is due not so much to the restoration of the traditional global equilibrium as to the gradual formation of alternative trade alliances and regional blocs that are consolidating on the basis of political identity, ideological proximity, or strategic trust.⁴¹ This shift is due to a change in the logic of world politics: the constraining effect of bipolar confrontation is a thing of the past, and some regional powers have opened up opportunities for independent positioning, independent of major players. While their role used to be subordinated to the will of dominant centers, they are now increasingly seeking to implement their own foreign policy scenarios, form regional alliances, and initiate transnational projects.

In some cases, this even leads to claims to regional leadership or local hegemony. The consequences of this dynamic are controversial for the entire international system.⁴² On the one hand, new growth points are emerging that stimulate the development of regional processes, increase the variability of actors, and enrich the palette of global influences. On the other hand, the system itself is becoming more fragmented, prone to internal contradictions that can generate instability and conflict in the event of a clash of competing trends and projects. In this context, the example of Turkey is illustrative, as it is strengthening its role in the international arena, demonstrating a controversial and multi-vector foreign policy and economic growth. Authors believe that the best example of polycentrism is the redistribution of GDP on a global scale (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Results and forecasts of GDP dynamics of new players in the period up to 2060 (France, the United Kingdom, Germany, Japan, Turkey, Brazil, Indonesia)

⁴¹ Metelenko, N. G., Kovalenko, O. V., Makedon, V., Merzhynskyi, Y. K., & Rudych, A. I. (2019). Infrastructure security of formation and development of sectoral corporate clusters. *Journal of Security and Sustainability Issues*, 9(1), 77–89. [https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2019.9.1\(7\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2019.9.1(7))

⁴² Lama, F. (2023). *Id.*

Source: based on United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division⁴³

As can be seen from Figure 1 clearly shows that the “new” players in the world order have high forecasts for the development of their economies, which will only consolidate their status as part of the “core” of leading political players on the world stage in the second half of the 21st century. At the same time, the high dynamics of global change, the unpredictability of regional and transnational crises, and the multidimensionality of modern conflicts will require states to constantly review and adapt their foreign policies to new threat formats that do not fit into traditional security paradigms (Table 3).⁴⁴

Table 3. Modern manifestations and features of regionalization as the basis of political polycentrism

Regionalization factor	Accumulation of resource potential	Ensuring national security	Political expediency and results	Polycentric manifestations
Macro-regional complexes	Growth of economic potential of regional associations (e.g., Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank)	Formation of regional security structures	Macro-regions as new centers of political influence	Strengthening regional civilizational identities
Regional leaders	Economic growth of countries (India, China) contributes to regional	Regional powers assume responsibility for security in their areas	Growth of political autonomy of regional leaders	Formation of unique cultural codes of regions

⁴³ United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division. (2024). *World population prospects 2024* (28th ed.). <https://population.un.org/wpp/>

⁴⁴ Pajak, K., Omelyanenko, V., Makedon, V., Shevchenko, V., & Ovcharenko, I. (2020). Raising the level of financial security of the enterprise based on the basic risks differentiation. *Journal of Security and Sustainability Issues*, 10(1), 115–130. [https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2020.10.1\(9\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2020.10.1(9))

	dominance			
Integration and confrontation on polycentrism	Competition between regional economic platforms	Conflicts for control over regional security spaces	Regional platforms as subjects of global politics	Clash of civilizational narratives in competition
Regional polarity	Economic mosaicism through regional specialization	Regional security systems instead of global hegemony	Local dominance of regional powers within their zones	Regional cultures as the basis of the mosaic structure
Decentralized polycentrism	Interregional economic coalitions for global influence	Flexible security alliances beyond regional borders	Projection of political influence of regional leaders on the global stage	Intercultural ties as a basis for new alliances
Global challenges and balance	Cooperation in solving economic problems (e.g., inequality)	Balance of power to avoid global conflicts	Harmonization of rules of behavior for a multipolar system	Combining national values with universal values

Source: author's own elaboration

In a situation of intensifying competition between the leading powers, both at the global and regional levels, when the search for a model of sustainable multipolar equilibrium becomes more relevant, which would not only serve as the basis for international stability but also contribute to a constructive solution to global problems: from environmental degradation to human rights violations, from socio-economic inequality to armed conflicts, the war in Ukraine and the serial military conflict between Israel and Iran are examples of global influence. Thus, looking at polycentrism through the lens of regionalization allows us to formulate several fundamental conclusions. First, the multipolar structure of the world order is being formed on the basis of strengthening regional integration processes, which are structural elements of the global system. Secondly, the growing potential of regional powers, combined with the weakening of traditional hegemony, contributes to the formation of a new configuration

of influence, which at the same time implies a greater differentiation of centers of power.

5. DISCUSSION

The holistic conclusions of the study confirm the scientific relevance of the concept of polycentrism as a defining feature of the modern geopolitical order. At the same time, the findings not only support existing scientific views, but also significantly expand them, providing a more detailed and multidimensional vision of this phenomenon. In particular, the findings are in line with Ashford and Cooper⁴⁵ and Chan,⁴⁶ who view the world through the prism of decentralized multipolarity, where there are several centers of influence that may be unequal in scale or resources. However, unlike these authors, who limit their analysis to the macro-geopolitical level, the article systematically structures polycentrism in key areas: economic, security, cultural, and political.

The study complements the views of Burton⁴⁷ and Morin and Couette,⁴⁸ who focus on the processes of power dispersion. Authors have developed this approach and emphasized the role of semi-peripheral states and regional integration associations in the formation of new centers of power. This presentation is in direct contrast to the traditional view of the unipolar nature of the world order, which is still inherent in some contemporary theories, such as Thapa⁴⁹ and Røren,⁵⁰ which, despite recognizing multipolar trends, do not let go of the unipolar model deeply enough. A particular achievement is the integration of three methodological approaches: geopolitical spatial analysis, global scenario modeling, and civilizational systems analysis. This became the basis for the presentation of polycentrism as a multi-level, complex structure in the coordinates of political present. While some scholars, such as Ablazov et al.⁵¹ and Kholod et al.,⁵² have already drawn attention to the importance of the spatial factor, their approaches did not take into account the cultural, civilizational, and institutional components that were combined in the proposed systemic analysis.

Separate vectors are aimed at the issue of strategic flexibility of semi-peripheral countries, which is in line with the views of Buxton et al.⁵³ and Richey.⁵⁴ In the field of

⁴⁵ Ashford, E., & Cooper, E. (2023). *Id.*

⁴⁶ Chan, B. (2025). *Id.*

⁴⁷ Burton, G. (2021). *Id.*

⁴⁸ Morin, J.-F., & Couette, C. (2025). *Id.*

⁴⁹ Thapa, R. (2025). *Id.*

⁵⁰ Røren, P. (2024). *Id.*

⁵¹ Ablazov, I. et al. (2021). *Id.*

⁵² Kholod, B. et al (2020). *Id.*

⁵³ Buxton, N. Et al. (2025). *Id.*

⁵⁴ Richey, M. (2020). *Id.*

this study, these views are complemented by the concept of “open regional leadership, which implies that regional actors are not limited to intra-regional activities but actively interact outside their macro-areas”, forming situational coalitions. These achievements have significantly enriched the understanding of polycentrism, especially in the context of the concept of “regional polarity” proposed by Cooley and Nexon⁵⁵ and Attinà,⁵⁶ but insufficiently developed in terms of global influence mechanisms.

One of the controversial issues is the potential transition of the world order to a bipolar model, which is actively discussed by Bomassi⁵⁷ and Peters⁵⁸ in connection with the growing Sino-US security confrontation. However, the results show that the dominant scenario is still the multipolar dynamics, especially given the growing role of countries such as India, Turkey, and Brazil. These facts are confirmed by empirical data and are consistent with the UN forecasts.⁵⁹ The scientific contribution of the current study is also in the conceptualization of polycentrism as a systemic feature of the international system that changes the paradigm of political competition: instead of hierarchical structures and hegemony, flexible alliances, situational partnerships, and strategic co-optation dominate. This scientific position develops the ideas of Thunder,⁶⁰ who proposes the concept of a “polycentric republic”, and complements the work of Lofthouse and Kral,⁶¹ who consider polycentrism as a tool for solving complex, “tangled” problems in international relations.

In practical terms, the results obtained are important for adapting the foreign policy strategies of states to the realities of the fragmented international environment. In particular, the proposed structural model of the polycentric world can be used as an analytical tool for assessing the international position of individual countries and formulating an adaptive foreign policy.

CONCLUSION

6.

The modern system of international relations is undergoing a profound evolution, which is reflected in the formation of a polycentric structure of the world order. This process is not only a consequence of the weakening dominance of individual global leaders, but also forms the result of a fundamental change in the distribution of power and influence, within which the role of new actors is growing, including countries that previously did not influence global processes, as well as regional associations. The

⁵⁵ Cooley, A., & Nexon, D. (2020). *Id.*

⁵⁶ Attinà, F. (2025). *Id.*

⁵⁷ Bomassi, L. (2025). *Id.*

⁵⁸ Peters, M. A. (2023). *Id.*

⁵⁹ United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division. (2024). *Id.*

⁶⁰ Thunder, D. (2025). *Id.*

⁶¹ Lofthouse, J. K., & Kral, L. (2025). *Id.*

study identified key factors contributing to the formation of a multipolar world. These include increased regional integration, the desire of states for strategic independence, and a rethinking of global governance models in the context of modern threats. It is established that polycentrism is taking on a specific form, and this is not just an even distribution of forces, but a complex, multi-vector architecture where each actor can have its own influence, while maintaining a high degree of fragmentation of the international system.

The article examines the interrelationships between regionalization processes and the emergence of a new global order. Regional integration mechanisms are now not only instruments of economic interaction, but also autonomous poles of power capable of influencing the security situation, forming new norms and cultural identities. As the positions of traditional hegemony weaken, it is regional groupings that are taking on the task of filling the power vacuum, offering a different logic of strategic interaction, such as through situational coalitions, flexible alliances, and pragmatic arrangements, regardless of ideological overlap.

Changes in global leadership do not mean the end of the US role as the world's leading power, but they do indicate a shift in emphasis toward collective responsibility, multilateralism, and new centers of influence. Among them: China, India, Turkey, Brazil, and Indonesia, which are actively involved in shaping the new rules of the global game. The author also analyzes the evolution of conflicts: classical military confrontations are increasingly being replaced by hybrid, cyber and information forms of warfare. It is proposed to consider polycentrism not just as an analytical concept, but as a model of a new type of global governance that requires a revision of international law, security principles and the institutional structure of world politics.

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